

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION IN SOCIETY

Nurmatov Azizbek NuralievichTeacher of the Department of Psychology
of Tashkent University of Applied Sciencese-mail : aziz.nurmatov.94@mail.ru Tel: +99891225-02-20

Abstract: The main types of education are family education and social education. In the course of the historical development of society, the importance of social education in the formation of a person is increasing. Education is an important function of social life. Education is essential for society to survive and progress. Through education, the inheritance of the material and spiritual wealth of the past is ensured: the growing young generation enriches it with the experiences of the past. Education plays a leading role in the individual development, moral and physical development of a person.

Key words: upbringing, psychology, society, behavior, age periods, temperament, character.

Another important task of the family is education. Mental, physical, moral and aesthetic education of children is founded in the family. The family is responsible not only for laying the foundation of the building called man, but also until its last brick is laid. A parent is an artist, a child is a work of art, and the process of education is art itself. After we gained independence, the restoration of our national values and our national customs and traditions, which our people have been preserving since time immemorial (in addition to parents, grandparents, relatives, and neighborhood influence in child education) are of great importance in this regard. But sometimes, as a result of the weakening of the educational task of the family and the lack of propaganda work, the appearance of bad habits (drinking, smoking, drug addiction, being influenced by various religious trends, embarking on the path of spiritual

corruption) in the behavior of family members. is one of the worrying cases. Forming and educating a perfect citizen of society is part of the task of the modern family.

Because the socialization of the individual takes place first in the family. Through upbringing in the family, a certain political-ideological outlook, moral norms and behavior patterns, and physical qualities are inculcated in a person. It is not for nothing that it is said in our people that "a bird does what it sees in its nest". As a result of the socialization process that takes place in the family, a person learns social norms and values and enters social life.

Interpretation of the concept of education in pedagogical psychology. Education is the process of formation and development of a person's consciousness in accordance with the goals and tasks of a particular society , a set of all influences aimed at active socio-economic and cultural participation of people. Education is closely related to education . Education is an important means of education, and technology, literature, art, mass media and means of propaganda (press, radio, television) have a great impact on education .

In the primitive society, education could not be considered as a separate activity, it consisted of simply assimilating the life experiences of the older generation by the younger generation. Education was carried out mainly in the process of working, as well as during various customs and games.

It is primarily aimed at the physical development of the growing generation. Due to the existence of classes in the primitive society, all children received almost the same education. The uneven division between men and women creates a disparity in the education of boys and girls .

With the emergence of classes, education became class-based. The exploiting class used it to strengthen their rule. During the period of slavery, wealthy people were brought up and educated in various educational institutions of that time . Slaves and their children were trained for hard physical labor. During feudalism, education was carried out in a stratified manner.

Family education - education of children in the family by parents, guardians or adults. It plays an important role in the all-round development of the young generation. A permanent educational force in family education is family order, that is, the relationship of family members to each other, behavior of parents and other adults, cultural and political level, family budget, living conditions and behavior. The more organized the family is, the more sincere the relationship between its members is, the more successful the child's upbringing will be. Family education will be just as successful. Family education starts from the child's early infancy. In the family, importance is attached to his health, physical development, proper nutrition, sleeping regime, cleanliness and so on.

Due to the strong imitation of others at a young age, adults in the family should not allow him to behave inappropriately. It is necessary not to allow them to interfere with the mental development of the child and the formation of positive feelings in him. The mental development of the child and the formation of positive feelings in him are also important from the very early age. As the child gets older, family education becomes more complicated. Children of preschool age are very curious and eager for everything. During this period, it is necessary to strictly control the behavior of the child in the family, to encourage creative activity in him, to give importance to the growth of his abilities. Establishing a suitable regime for the child's life in the family makes him accustomed to being orderly, develops the ability to manage his own behavior, and the game occupies a central place in the life of children of preschool age. Parents should supervise their children and their games from time to time to regularly study child hygiene procedures and physical exercises from a very young age (child and adolescent hygiene). In this work, the example of adults is important.

Peculiarities of education at different ages of childhood

They say that there is no peace at home, there is no peace anywhere. In fact, a person who is happy in his family is in a good mood, cheerful and happy everywhere - at work, on the street, in the circle of friends, on a walk. However, if a person is unhappy in the family, is not satisfied with his home, and considers himself unhappy,

then this unhappiness always casts a shadow, and the edge of the person's heart is always sad.

The stability of the atmosphere of harmony and family happiness in the family depends on several factors, for example, deep affection between the spouses, mutual respect and friendship, dignity between family members, mutual loyalty, etc. Among these factors, the relationship between parents and adults and children has a special place. We want to focus on this important factor here.

The elderly, parents, through their life experiences, are aware of the psychological characteristics of children. But most of this awareness is general and not based on the age and individual characteristics of children. Because of this, in many families, there is a "chaos of misunderstanding" between parents and children. This attitude should be radically changed.

Parents need to know their children's psychological characteristics well. At the same time, they should form the feelings of warm love, respect and regard for the elderly as ideals in children as well. Mild and rough treatment of children will certainly leave a positive or negative impression on their mental world. The result of such an impression affects children's games and reading activities. Accordingly, there can be a truly harmonious atmosphere in the family only when the elderly and parents deeply know their children's character, interest, and in general their spiritual world.

As young children enter school, playtime grows. Dealing with children unfamiliar to the teacher creates an uncomfortable situation for them. In order to prevent some children from such a situation, it is necessary not to pamper him too much, not to fulfill his demands all the time.

A child with a third trait does not have a bright mood, so it is difficult to make him laugh, make him angry or generally upset his mood. Even when everyone is laughing loudly about something in the arms of the family or at school, he remains calm. Even when unpleasant events happen, he does not disturb his peace. His actions will be weak and expressionless. However, he is distinguished from others by his enthusiasm and hard work. The nerve of such a child is strong, balanced, but has a

sluggish character. He is not like other children because of his endurance and ability to behave in different situations. The speed of their movements, the level of speech is low, their mental states have become internal experiences. The folk saying "find it inside" is suitable for such boys and girls.

Fourthly, a group-specific child has the characteristic of sensitivity, but his nerves are weak and far from active. That's why tears come to his eyes from something insignificant. Such teenage boys and girls are very irritable and cannot get involved in doing any work. Not confident in his own strength, he is shy not only in school and public places, but also in the family. If faced with a little difficulty, he will give up everything. He is distrustful and suspicious of the happenings and events.

Feelings of inclination towards the opposite sex appear during adolescence. It is natural to read physical books, indulge in the inner world, withdraw into solitude, read romantic books, watch movies, listen to the words of older people. Also, at this age, boys and girls begin to pay more attention to their appearance. Boys have a desire to dress more correctly and look in the mirror. Girls also look more in the mirror, want to put on make-up and be beautiful. This is also natural.

Because educating one's appearance is an important characteristic of a person, therefore it cannot be denied.

A sense of size arises during puberty. They begin to feel more sorry for adults, what they do, how they behave. The behavior of adults towards them, which was the same as that of the previous young child, evokes an unpleasant feeling. The main reason for the conflict between parents, teachers and teenagers is the fact that adults do not consider their wishes and desires. they don't notice. Cases of inappropriate rebuke, cutting, and ordering every request by adults cause bad experiences in a teenager.

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